

Tashkent and worked as a hired worker in many places. That's about it, in his epic «O'tmishim» he wrote:

Qarol bo'lib ishladim,
Bir burda non tishladim.
Turmushim kun-kun og'ir
Bo'ldi, yiqildim oxir...

During his 40-year life, Elbek wrote poems and epics, textbooks and manuals, wrote prose works and parables. «Elbek started the parable. Not through translation took the path of giving birth to parables. There is another person on this road has not been seen», - wrote literary critic Abdurahman Sa'diy.

Indeed, in the 20s and 30s of the last century, Elbek wrote «Maymunning qoziligi», «Jinning olov yoqishi», «Kampirning tovuqlari», «Ikki tulki», «Kuchsizlar dunyosi», «Yer bilan tog' o'rtasida», «Yelkan bilan kema», «Qora qushlar bilan toshbaqalar», «Ot bilan Odam», «Chumoli ila Chivin», «Quyruqsiz maymun», «Qaysi biri bo'ri» like different topics and different levels created parables. They have the ideas of fighting for rightness and justice pushed.

«Which in the parable of «one is a wolf», Elbek refers to the promises of the Bolsheviks about freedom and independence skepticism was expressed. Tsarist Russia is really Turkestan conquered and established the Wolf's violent attitude towards the Sheep. And the Bolsheviks, saying that they will save Turkestan from the tsarism, changed it had begun to understand the complexity of colonialism. Elbek, the same situation noticed and expressed figuratively in the example:

Bo'rimi yo aytgil endi kim vahshiy?
Outqarding sen meni bo'ri tishidan.
Hamda qo'rqinch shul o'limning vahmidan
Eng so'ng o'zing bo'ridan-da o'zdiriding,
Ko'rdim endi chin bo'ri ham sen o'zing!

Elbek wrote many funny poems for children. He announced in collections such as «Ko'zgu», «Yolqinlar», «Bahor», «G'unchalar». This to introduce children to nature in their poems, to insects, the Motherland in exchange for arousing feelings of love for plants and birds tried to teach the lesson of love.

Along with this work, Elbek also taught and wrote used textbooks in the course of his work. He writes about it like this:

«The problem cannot be solved by teaching from books alone. Maybe, ul to be able to animate the things written in the book and to understand what they have learned should be implemented. Of course, although there are few teachers for this work, should be looked at a work that shows the ways of learning like these books their forgiveness is touching. They were written for kazakh-kyrgyz schools with this wish in mind knowledge of this work accepted in primary schools that it is also used in Uzbek schools of the Pedagogical Commission of the Council

I fulfilled this task as he found me worthy and handed it over to me.» (September 1923)

Elbek for students of the 2nd-4th grade «Yozuv yo'llari» (1921), «O'rnak», «Go'zal yozg'ichlar» (1925) has created training manuals and collections. Folk art Bo'stanliq in 1921-22 in order to collect and study its materials district, and in 1932 to Ohangaron and Chirchik districts and Fergana organized an expedition to the valley. Elbek collected as a result of scientific trips widely used the materials in the «Bilim» collection for grades 1-3. «Ashulalar to'plami» (published 2 times in 1934-35), «Laparlar» and he published the collections «Ertaklar» (1935).

He considered Fitrat, who gave him the nickname Elbek, as his spiritual teacher and wrote the poem «Til» in response to his poem. He was accused of nationalism during the years of repression, and on August 7, 1937 was imprisoned as an «enemy of the people» and deprived of liberty for 12 years done. In 1938, he died of a serious illness in Magadan. However, his modest creativity is still with our students and teachers today serves as a special guide for.

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1920-1940 YILLARDA YARATILGAN DARSLIK LARNING G'OYAVIY YO'NALISHI

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Annotatsiya. *Ma'rifatparvarlar yaratgan darsliklarda ilm va ustozlarni ardoqlash g'oyalarining ustivorligi, ijobiy axloqiy sifatlarning ulug'lanishi yaqqol ko'rinadi. Darsliklarda mavzular so'ngida qissadan hissa tarzidagi g'oyaviy-mantiqiy xulosalar va xalq maqollari berilib, ulardagi barcha she'r, qissa, hikoya va ertaklar o'quvchilarning yoshiga mosligi bilan ahamiyatlidir.*

Kalit so'zlar: *darslik, mazmun, matn, ma'rifatparvar, kitob, boshlang'ich ta'lim, savod.*

Yangi madaniy harakatlikning namoyondalari bo'lgan ma'rifatparvarlarning darsliklari ko'rgazmalilik, osondan-qiyinga, oddiydan-murakkabga o'tish, matn bayonining sodda va tushunarligi, integrativ metod kabilarga asoslanadi. Darsliklardagi matnlarni mazmun va xarakteriga qarab 3 guruhga bo'lish mumkin:

1) folklor hamda mumtoz adabiyot namunalari olingan o'quv materiallari Masalan: Ali Asqar Kalinning «Muallimi soniy» darsligidagi ayrim matnlar, Shakuriyning «Jameul-hikoyat» darsligidagi o'quv materiallari kabilar;

2) rus mumtoz adabiyotidan qilingan tarjimalar asosida tanlangan o'quv materiallari Masalan, M.Behbudiy «Muntaxabi jug'rofiyai umumiy» darsligini tuzishda Shamsiddinbek Somiyning 6 jildlik mashhur «Qomus ul-a'lom» va I.Gasprinskiyning «Turkiston ulamosi» kitoblaridagi hujjat va dalillarga tayanadi; A.Sa'diy «Og'zaki va yozma adabiyotning nazariyasi va amaliyoti» darsligini yaratishda Shalgina, Veselovskiy, Buxarin, Lunacharskiy, Lvov-Rogachevskiy, Frich, Kulikovskiy larning asarlaridan foydalangan;

3) darslik mualliflari ijodiga mansub bo'lgan, ular tomonidan mustaqil tarzda tuzilgan o'quv materiallari, masalan, Shakuriyning «Jameul-hikoyat» darsligidagi hikoyalar.

Ma'rifatparvarlarning darsliklarida do'stlik, ezgulik madh etiladi. Aksariyat darsliklardagi hikoyalar o'zaro mantiqan bog'langan bo'lib, biri ikkinchisini to'ldirib boradi. Darsliklardan o'quv materiali sifatida xalq maqollari ham o'rin olgan.

Yuqoridagilar asosida quyidagilarni ta'kidlash mumkin. Ma'rifatparvarlarning boshlang'ich ta'lim islohoti sohasida ilgari surgan g'oyalari, asosan, quyidagilardan iborat:

- boshlang'ich ta'lim samaradorligini ta'minlash uchun savodga o'rgatish usulini o'zgartirish;

- o'qitishda ko'rgazmalilikka e'tibor berish;

- maktabni muayyan didaktik qurilishga ega bo'lgan, ta'lim amaliyotiga yaroqli, ona tilidagi darsliklar va ularni o'qitish metodikasi bilan ta'minlash;

- eski maktab va madrasalardagi o'qitish tizimini tubdan yangilash;

- ta'lim islohoti g'oyalarini targ'ib qilishda matbuotdan unumli foydalanish;

- ta'lim tizimida o'zgarishlarni amalga oshirish uchun jahondagi ilg'or tajribalarni ta'lim amaliyotiga ijodiy tatbiq etish;

- nafaqat o'g'il, balki qiz bolalarning ham yetarlicha bilim olishlariga imkoniyat yaratish kabilar.

Turkistonda darsliklar yaratilishi tarixi bevosita sinf-dars tizimiga asoslangan yangicha ta'limning shakllanishi va rivojlanishi bilan uzviy bog'liq bo'lib, bular ta'lim mazmuni, shakli, o'qitish mezonlari, manbalari, g'oyaviy yo'nalishi kabilarga bevosita ta'sir ko'rsatdi.

Biz quyida Milliy uyg'onish davrida yaratilgan darsliklarda mualliflar tayangan didaktik tamoyil va mezonlar haqida fikr yuritimiz.

1. Ma'rifatparvarlar darsliklar yaratishda, avvalo, o'z pedagogik tajribalariga, so'ngra rus pedagoglari maslahatlariga amal qilganlar. Masalan, Behbudiy «Muntaxabi jug'rofiyai umumiy» darsligini tuzishda tatar pedagogi Ismoilbek Gasprinskiy maslahatlariga amal qilgan.

2. Darsliklarni qiyosiy tahlil etish ularning tarkibiy tuzilishi, tayanilgan didaktik tamoyil va mezonlarida birlik mavjudligini ko'rsatdi. Masalan, Behbudiyning «Muntaxabi jug'rofiyai umumiy» darsligi bilan M.Abdurashidxonovning «Adibi soniy» darsliklarining tarkibiy tuzilishi, tayanilgan didaktik tamoyil va mezonlarida o'xshashlik mavjud.

3. Darsliklardagi o'quv materiallari o'zining pedagogik ahamiyatiga ko'ra quyidagi yo'nalishlarda berilgan:

a) axloqiy tarbiyaga yo'naltirilgan pand-nasihati mazmunidagi o'quv materiallari, ular janr jihatdan hikoyat, masal, topishmoq, maqol kabilarga mansub;

b) darsliklarda taqdim etilgan o'quv materiallari oddiydan murakkabga borish tamoyilida joylashtirilgan.

Tanlangan o'quv materiallari mazmuni va joylashtirilish tartibiga ko'ra darsliklar, ulardagi matnlarning g'oyaviy-tarbiyaviy mazmuni o'xshash: tanlangan didaktik matnlar mazmun va shakliga ko'ra sharqona, milliy ruhga ega. Darsliklardagi o'quv materiallari pand-nasihati, matal, hikoyat, ertak kabilardan iborat didaktik matn shaklida berilgan. O'quv materiali tarkibida o'quvchilarda shakllantirilishi zarur bo'lgan ijobiy fazilatlariga ta'rif berilgan bo'lib, ularda go'zal axloq egasi bo'lgan insonning jamiyatdagi mavqei qay darajada yuksak bo'lishi lozimligi haqida fikr yuritiladi. Shuningdek, darsliklarga o'quv materiallari tanlashda o'quvchining yoshi, bilim darajasi hisobga olingan.

Tahlil etilgan darsliklarning o'zaro farqli jihatlari quyidagilardan iborat:

- muayyan fan sohalariga oid ma'lumotlardan, jumladan, tarix, geografiya, turk yoki fors-tojik tili, arifmetika va h.k.lardan foydalanilganligi;

- o'quv materiallarining ikkinchi qismi yoritilgan mavzuga oid savol-topshiriqlardan iboratligi;

- ayrim darsliklarga g'oyaviy-mafkuraviy o'quv materiallarining kiritilganligi.

Tahlillar asnosida darsliklarda berilgan o'quv materiallari quyidagi didaktik tamoyillar asosida tanlanganligi aniqlandi:

- **onglilik** va **faollik** asosiy didaktik tamoyil sifatida darsliklarga o'quv materiallarini tanlashga asos bo'lgan. Ta'lim jarayonida onglilik va faollik o'quv materiali mazmunidagi tushuncha, g'oya hamda dalillarni tahlil qilish, solishtirish, qiyoslash, umumlashtirish,